

Trust-based recommender system to solve the problem of cold start in social networks

1. Introduction

In cyberspace, social networks have been introduced as a new type of website and have found many users and fans. A social network is one of the types of social media, which is a place for the formation of virtual communities and networking of Internet users. A social network is a group of individuals or organizations with common interests and tastes that come together to achieve specific goals. The main reasons for creating social networks include personal, business, and scientific relationships, shared tastes and interests, and socio-political motivations [1]. Social networks have managed to attract significant Internet users. Some web analysts considered the future of cyberspace at the disposal of these types of sites.

The basic features of social networks are [2]:

1. A group of individuals or organizations that participate in a social network.
2. There is at least one connection between individuals or organizations in the network. If they are friends, there is a link between two people on the social network. For example, on Facebook, this relationship is called "friends".
3. There is a local assumption that relationships on social networks tend to cluster or group. This means that if person A is related to person B and person B is related to person C, there is a more than 50% chance that person A is related to person C.

Naturally, social networks can be represented by graphs. In a social network, individuals and organizations are considered as nodes, and the link between two nodes can be represented by an edge. We usually represent a social network as a graph $G(V, E)$ where V represents the vertices and equivalents of the node or network users and E represents the edges that are equivalent to the relationships between the vertices.

If there are n nodes in a social graph, there will be a maximum $\binom{n}{2}$ edge between the nodes.

The study of social network features and relationships between individuals and sections of a network with a network theory or graph approach is considered as an analysis of social networks. In other words, social network analysis is a kind of interdisciplinary study in various areas such as sociology, management, and organization, linguistics, economics and business, anthropology, etc. Exploring communities is useful for a variety of reasons. For example, users in a community who want to interact frequently, often have common interests, and to some extent trust each other. Facebook friends graph or a follower graph on Twitter or Google Plus are common instances. Therefore, surveying communities is useful for guiding the way of disseminating information, creating recommender systems, and explaining access control policies, and detecting fake accounts [3]. With the rapid growth of these sites, problems such as fake profiles, and online forgery [4] have been increased. The main risk is related

to the fact that anyone can create a profile to impersonate a real person on social media. Fake profiles can be exploited that resulted in online relationships with the target individual, especially online relationships with the victim's friends. Therefore, it is necessary to find fake users and remove them from the recommendation to other users in social networks.

Meanwhile, the cold start problem in the recommender system can cause a stagnation in the system and make the implementation of the recommendation difficult. Solving this problem can help recommender systems to provide better recommendations. To this end, we will apply demographic information of users. Extracting the nonlinear relationships between latent factors and demographic information is a challenging task that cannot be adequately addressed using statistical methods or simple machine learning algorithms. Therefore, deep learning is used to do this [5].

2. Related Works

In this paper [6], researchers proposed a new tensor factorization model named TrustTF, which mainly works as follows: (1) Using user's social trust information and implicit feedback to extend the bias tensor factorization (BiasTF), effectively alleviate data sparsity problem and improve the recommendation accuracy; (2) Dividing user's trust relationship into unilateral trust and mutual trust, which makes better use of user's social information. Base on researcher's knowledge, this is the first work to consider the effects of both user trust and implicit feedback on the basis of the BiasTF model. The experimental results in two real-world data sets demonstrate that the TrustTF proposed in this paper can achieve higher accuracy than BiasTF and other social recommendation methods.

The proposed unified approach of this article [7] uses explicit trust, implicit trust, and user preference similarity to create a unified rating profile for the target user to produce more powerful and accurate recommendations. The proposed unified approach also enhances the recommendation performance of CF-based recommender systems

when only a limited set of ratings is available. Experiments are performed on three publicly available datasets which are FilmTrust, CiaoDVD, and Epinions. Comparison of obtained results is made with traditional similarity measures as well as up-to-date trust-based approaches. The results show that the proposed unified approach is superior to existing approaches in terms of both predictive and classification-based accuracy measures.

This paper proposes [8] a collaborative filtering recommendation algorithm (ETBRec), which not only considers the trust difference between users but also proposes the definition of experts and considers the direct impact of expert users on prediction ratings and the trustees' indirect impact of ratings. Among them, the trust difference is realized through trust metrics, including direct trust metrics and indirect trust metrics; the selection of expert users takes into account the user's degree of trust and user rating attitude; experimental comparisons with various social recommendation algorithms and related recommendation algorithms on the Ciao and

Douban datasets. The experimental results show that the ETBRec algorithm performs better on some evaluation indexes such as mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean squared error (RMSE).

This study [9] suggests a novel trust-based matrix factorization technique referred to as CFMT, which uses the social network data in the recommendation process by modeling user's roles as trustees and trusters, given the trust network's structural information. The proposed method seeks to lower the sparsity of the data and the cold start problem by integrating information sources including ratings and trust statements into the recommendation model, an attempt by which significant superiority over state-of-the-art approaches is demonstrated an empirical examination of real-world datasets.

The aim of this paper [10] is to present a comparative analysis of different trust metrics in the context of the type of trust definition of TBRS. Also, the study accomplishes on twenty-four trust metrics in terms of the methodology, trust properties & measurement, validation approaches, and the experimented dataset.

It has been used in recommender systems to solve cold-start problem, better estimate the interaction functions, and extract deep feature representations, among other facets that plague the traditional recommender systems. As big data is becoming more prevalent, there is a need to use tools that can take advantage of such explosive data. An extensive study on recommender systems using deep learning has been performed in this paper [11]. The literature review spans in-depth analysis and comparative study of the research domain. The paper exhibits a vast range of scope for efficient recommender systems in future.

3- Objectives and Hypothesis

The objectives and hypothesis of this study are as follows:

- General objectives
 - Investigate the analysis and detection of irregular techniques in social networks.
 - Providing an algorithm to identify fraudulent users or fake nodes based on trust criterion of each node.

- Alternative objectives
 - Providing a solution for cold start problem
 - Investigating the characteristics of social networks
- Hypothesis
 1. Can fake nodes be detected using the trust criterion of node?
 2. Is it efficient to use node trust in detecting fraud?
 3. Is it efficient to use demographic information for the cold start problem?
 4. Is it efficient to use node trust for cold start problem?

4- Innovation

With the advent of virtual social networks, a new form of life was formed in cyberspace and the relationships between people were differed compared to their traditional form, which resulted in an undeniable impact on social relationships. The social network is one of the most popular media that have a large audience, especially young people. The challenge of privacy is one of the most important issues that has always been raised about social networks. Internet

users in this network publish a part of their personal information on the Internet, which can be dangerous for them, and there is a possibility of misuse and threats by some people from your information. Due to the impossibility of identifying the real identity of the members and also the impossibility of controlling the content produced by the users of social networks, we are witnessing negative consequences in these networks.

According to the behavior of users, the proposed algorithm assigns labels such as power, credibility, comment rating, and likes, to each user (node). Based on these parameters, node trusts are calculated and classified into the corresponding fake and real classes. When nodes are tagged based on their behavior, it is easier for the user to accept or ignore a friendship request from such a node. We have also provided a solution to the cold problem.

5- Research Method

This study is aimed to provide a method for recommending to the real users in social networks using in-depth learning. Deep learning is one

of the subsets of machine learning and can be used in both supervised and unsupervised learning. In this study, supervised learning will be used as the following steps. Supervised learning means that the data set is divided into two sets of training and test data, which are trained using the following steps to identify real and fake users, and the test set to properly execute the algorithm for detection according to the training set.

The proposed method is carried out in 7 steps Which is shown in Figure 1 .

Fig1. Flowchart of the proposed method

The set of users is $U = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N\}$. In the first step, the power of each node is calculated based on internal and external relationships with other nodes [12], with the difference that in addition to the friends of user U , users who have user U in their friends list are also checked. To this end, we use the adjacency matrix. Then, a score is assigned to each node based on its behavior. In the second step, the output of the previous step is used as the input. To estimate the validity of each node, first the oracle function is used, which is the properties of the trust function. If this value is higher than our selected threshold, the node is considered as legal and real. This function helps to create a set of real nodes. Then friendship requests and the available friends in the network are used to calculate trust. Here, the ratio of F_U to Z_U are calculated, where F_U represents the number of friendship requests accepted by U and Z_U represents the number of friendship requests made by U to other users. We now use the following equation to calculate the trust score of each node:

$$TS(U_i) = \frac{F_U}{Z_U}$$

Here F_U is the number of friendship requests accepted by the network nodes sent by node U and Z_U is the number of friendship requests sent by the node U.

In the third step, the power of the network in the directed graph is calculated as a sum of its degree and then, its score is calculated. In our proposed activity, the guiding graph is considered. Here, a degree of network is considered in which the friendship request is accepted by the node that is created outside of this degree as a friendship request by that particular node, and is accepted by the relevant nodes. If the power of the node is more than half of the nodes in the network, that node is selected as the strongest node. Network power can be easily calculated from the adjacency matrix.

In the fourth step, the rank of the comments is calculated in such a way that the number of comments left by the user is divided by all the comments left and the number obtained is considered as the rank of the comments:

$$RC = \frac{\sum user's\ comment}{\sum_{i=1}^N user's\ comment_i}$$

Also, the rank of user likes is calculated based on the following formula:

$$RI = \frac{\sum user's\ like}{\sum_{i=1}^N user's\ like_i}$$

Finally, in the fifth step, the trust of each user is calculated based on the following formula:

$$UT = \sum TS + P + RC + RI$$

Here a threshold credit is defined. If the obtained U_T is greater than this value, the user is recognized as a real user and otherwise as a suspicious user and goes to the next section.

Threshold credit is defined as follows:

$$UT(n) > \delta \leftrightarrow O(n) = 1$$

One of the problems of recommender system is cold start problem.

The cold start problem occurs when there is not enough and necessary

information (ratings) in the system in order to submit a proposal. For example, users who have just joined the social network and do not have any rank, are known as fake users in the proposed system. To overcome this problem, we will use the information of user registration time in the network. If the registration date is less than 1 month, the following threshold is calculated for their rank, which is considered as a real user if the rank is higher than the threshold and is included in the recommendation process.

$$UT(n) > \frac{\delta}{2} \leftrightarrow O(n) = 1$$

In the sixth step, to make recommendations to other users, similar users to the target user are extracted using the cosine criterion, based on the trust rating and offered to the target user.

Finally, in the last step, the proposed method will be evaluated with other available methods based on evaluation criteria such as mean absolute error (MAE) and mean square error (RMSE). Also, valid datasets in this field will be used for this study.

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